

PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF A PICTURE MODEL IN A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: This thesis presents an analysis of the PICRAT model on the needs, advantages and limitations of technology integration models in the preparation of future technology teachers for professional activity. PIC (passive, interactive, creative) refers to the learner's response to technology in a given learning scenario. RAT (substitution, augmentation, modification) describes the impact of technology on a teacher's previous practice. With the development and expansion of digital technologies and increasing demands on future computer science teachers, PICRAT is a useful model for teaching technology integration that is clear, relevant, and effective, emphasizes technology as a means to an end, and provides comprehensive balances.

Key words: "PICRAT" educational resources, professional training of future teachers, PIC, RAT, digitization of education.

Introduction.

In the process of globalization and internationalization of education in the world, professional-pedagogical training of future teachers in the conditions of digitized education, improvement of the diagnostic system for the formation of their pedagogical activity, creation of an electronic monitoring system for the formation of creative potential, improvement of the methodical system for the introduction of digital technology of development, specialists Scientific research works are being carried out to improve the theoretical and methodological bases of development on the basis of various technologies in preparation for professional pedagogical activities. At the same time, special attention is being paid to the improvement of the models of developing the creative potential of future teachers and their professional training based on digital technologies.

Development of socio-pedagogical technologies for improving professional and pedagogical training of future teachers in the conditions of digitized education in our republic in recent years, use of digitized, innovative educational technologies and pedagogical models in education and development of future teachers " individualization of educational processes on the basis of digital

technologies, development of distance education services", normative bases for adapting the material and technical bases of higher education institutions to the conditions of digital education are being created. "Further improvement of the continuing education system, increasing the possibilities of quality education services, training of highly qualified personnel in line with the modern needs of the labor market" Priority tasks such as raising an advanced generation, creating a reserve of competent scientific and pedagogical personnel in higher education institutions"4 are defined in the Strategy of Actions, and the Decree "On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" as a result, in the conditions of digitized education, the pedagogical possibility of improving the professional-pedagogical preparation of future teachers and wide use of digital technologies will be expanded.

Creative modular technologies for the formation and development of skills and competences for working with digital technologies for students of informatics and other majors based on the improvement of the professional and pedagogical training of future teachers in the conditions of digitized education in world higher education institutions are being applied to the process. "The 1st International Convention on the Study of Science" (2014) in cooperation with the US National Academy of Sciences, OECD, UNESCO, East China and Shanghai Universities; training of future informatics specialists based on the standard requirements of CSTA K-12 CS Standards (2017), introduction of advanced methods and methods of teaching based on modern pedagogical and innovative technologies in accordance with world education standards, pedagogical staff in digitalized education in improving the training system, ensuring the unity of technological innovations in the conditions of digital education in European countries, Russia, the USA, China, Japan, and South Korea in terms of the conceptual foundations of education, coherence, continuity, competence development technologies1, scientific and Systematic work is being carried out to improve the professional pedagogical training of future teachers by creating a modern pedagogical environment.

Analysis and results:

Integrating instructional technologies requires educators to contend with ever-changing, politically-influenced professional demands, ever-evolving educational technology resources, and changing needs across content disciplines and contexts. Educators cannot predict how their students will use educational technology in the future or how technology will change during their careers. Therefore, training student teachers to practice technology integration in

meaningful, effective, and sustainable ways is a challenging task. We propose a theoretical model, PICRAT, that addresses this need.

A variety of theoretical models are currently used to help student teachers conceptualize effective technology integration, including

Technology, Pedagogy and Content Knowledge - TPACK;

Change - Fill - Change - Redefine – SAMR;

Technology Integration Planning - TIP;

Technology integration matrix - TIM;

Technology acceptance model - TAM;

Levels of technology integration - LoTi;

Change - Amplification - Transformation - RAT;

Although these models are often referenced in the literature to underpin methodological approaches to educational technology learning, there is little to evaluate their effectiveness, accuracy, or value for improving educational technology learning or for instructional technology integration. Works of theoretical criticism and minimal evaluation can be found. Relatively few researchers have attempted to critically evaluate these models, classify and compare them, support their continued development, understand the assumptions and processes of their adoption, or explore what constitutes good theory in the field.

In other words, educational technologists are adversely affected by competing models without critically evaluating them, understanding their uses, and learning how they evolve over time. Failure to engage in critical discussion about the theory and reality that shapes practical technology integration has serious implications for practice.

A critical discussion of existing models and theoretical frameworks of practice is necessary, and we provide the following conceptual framework, including (a) what theoretical models are and why they are needed for teaching technology integration, (b) how they are perceived and when (c) what makes them good or bad, and (d) how effective are existing models of technology integration in teacher training. Against this background, we propose a new theoretical model, PICRAT, that can guide student teachers in developing technology integration literacy, based on previous work by Hughes et al.

As a theoretical model for guiding teachers' technology integration, PICRAT enables teachers to stimulate thinking, guide practice, and evaluate student teachers' work. Any theoretical model will explain certain features well and ignore others, but PICRAT is a student-centered, pedagogy-based model that can

be effective for the specific context of teacher education. , is understandable and usable by teachers because it guides the most useful ideas about technology.

The development of this model must begin by considering two of the most important questions that a teacher must think about and evaluate when using technology in teaching: time constraints, training constraints, and their free perspective on their teaching. . Based on research that emphasizes the need for models to focus on students, our first question is, "What are students doing with technology?" Recognizing the importance of teachers' reflection on their own pedagogical practices, our second question was: How does the use of technology affect teacher pedagogy?

Teachers' answers to these questions on a three-tiered response indicator comprise a model we call PICRAT.

PIC refers to the three options related to the first question (passive, interactive and creative); RAT represents three options for the second (substitution, amplification and transformation).

Conclusion.

PICRAT balances comprehensiveness and parsimony to provide educators with a conceptual tool that is clear, effective, and consistent with existing practices and expectations, avoiding technocentric thinking. Despite its ever-changing, policy-influenced and intensely contextual nature, the strengths of the PICRAT model are an educational and self-reflective tool that teachers can use to train teachers to effectively integrate technology. we emphasize as Along with this, in our future scientific research work, it is planned to apply the PICRAT model in various practices and pedagogical conditions, and at the same time, to describe general analyzes of theoretically based approaches to how effectively it can manage teachers' practice, thinking and pedagogical changes.

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